

Online Education: A Game changer in Modern Education

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Abstract:- E-resource is a broad term that emphasis of various way of information and publishing models, including OPACs, CD-ROMs, online databases, E-journals, E-books, internet resources, print-on-demand (POD), E-mail publishing, wireless publishing, electronic link, and web-Portal publishing, etc. Therefore, today all learners have a mislenious way of knowledge and information regarding their study. The E-resource is expedient to use, obtainable at a reasonable cost, and can be accessed from anywhere and by many users can concurrently, these databases are most advantageous utilize to put into the academic excellence and achievement of its user community. Due to the availability of e-resource users can quickly download the specified book and therefore the readers can bookmark a page, create remarks, emphasize passages, and save chosen text also the readers can comprise lexicon, and modifiable typescript sizes and styles. Hence, some issues and challenges also appeared in the way of the use of e-resource that is a deficiency of infrastructural facilities and lack of knowledge of use. In many libraries e-resources are not visible or accessible to the users as to where resources are physically available for browsing and use.

Keywords:- Online DBMS, Science, Technology, Education.

I. INTRODUCTION

E-resources are resources in which information is stored electronically and is accessible through electronic systems and networks. E-resource" is a broad term that includes a variety of publishing models, including OPACs, CD-ROMs, online databases, E-journals, E-books, internet resources, print-on-demand (POD), E-mail publishing, wireless publishing, electronic link, and web publishing, etc. In this context, the term primarily denotes "any electronic product that delivers a collection of data be it in text, numerical, graphical, or time based, as a commercially available. Computers and related electronic resources have come to play a central role in education. Moreover, electronic or e-resource is defined as a source that needs computer access or any electronic item for consumption that distributes a compilation of information, be it manuscript referring to a complete book as a commercially obtainable label that has been published with an aim to being marked.

The use of the Internet by research scholars, therefore, is an important area of study in today"s information environment. The Internet has nowadays become an important component in academic institutions as it plays a pivotal role in meeting the

information and communication needs of institutions. It makes it possible to access a wide range of information, such as up-to-date research reports, from anywhere in the world. It also enables scholars and academic institutions to disseminate information to a wider audience around the globe through having websites and a way to search for them and organize the output. The use of the Internet by research scholars, therefore, is an important area of study in today's information environment. The Internet has nowadays become an important component in academic institutions as it plays a pivotal role in meeting the information and communication needs of Institutions.

E-resources is that "Information (usually a file) which can be stored in the form electrical signal usually, but not necessary on a computer". Electronic journals are simply serial publications in which the end products are made available in digital formats and online whose contents may or may not be peer-reviewed.

II. ONLINE-RECOURSE AND EDUCATION

For a global audience, in India, many science journals, technology journals, and medical journals are now available online through the initiatives of the government and private non-profit publishers. Generally, demic libraries situated within the academic institutions are considered as the heart of the institution. Academic libraries are. It serves mainly for student research scholars, teaching and non-teaching staff of the institutions. The resources of the academic library belong to the courses offer by the institutions. Generally, all the academic libraries consist of textbooks, reference books, Journals, theses dissertations, project reports, maps, atlases, drawings, and magazines in both print and electronic formats. Also, academic libraries are subscribing to online journals, e-books, online databases for the benefit of students and scholars. The main objective of the academic library is to serve the academic community particularly their exams, preparation of seminars, conferences, symposiums, projects, and research work. So, offering orientation programs are essential to the users and it will improve the strength of the knowledge. Academic libraries are directing the users for searching the information from print or e-resources. Academic libraries provide the best information to its reader. University libraries are playing an important role in the academic community. It gives pleasure to the user and it also creates a learning environment in the university. The library is an important part of any academic institution through information distribution.

The online resources are helping to save the time of users and also to libraries. The academic library environment gives quality and quantity of information to the users through its collection and that is identified by an individual learner according to his/her experience, competence, and personal learning goals. The traditional and e-resources of the library's learning environment belong to the information related to the user's requirement; the ways information is being collected and distributed. Academic library resources are considered a good measure of an institution's excellence and quality. The information resources and services available in the institutional information systems must be capable of supporting research activities among the students and faculty members.

The library is an organized collection of printed books and periodicals of any other graphic and audiovisual materials and the services of the staff to provide the facilities such materials as are required to meet the information, research educational, or recreational needs of its user.

III. IMPORTANCE OF E-RESOURCES

E-resources play a vital role in the all over world, every user must know the importance of e-resources, it is accepted by all kind of people because of its accessibility, affordability, usability, and readability.

- The information preserves at standard intervals and can be reserved always up-to-date in electronic media.
- Smooth the progress of easy replication into new media and sharing the data.
- Incorporation of special media (Image, Sound, Video, etc.)
- Afford hyperlinks to related additional resources.
- The electronic resources unresponsive to environmental exposure and if handle with care, it will prove huge stability which cannot be attained on paper-based print media.
- Saves massive time by providing easy and immediate access without slaying time for processing, printing, binding, and delivery.
- It also saves the space of the library.
- It gives awareness to the user community such as PG students, research scholars, faculty, staff, etc.
- The user can get all the data in a digitalized format, so there is no need for printing and binding.
- The cost of e-resources is less than the print version.

IV. TYPES OF E-RESOURCES

Different types of e-resource available are not separate but in real related to each other.

A. E-Books

An E-Book is an electronic account of a conventional print book that can be read using a personal computer or by using an E-Book reader. Users can purchase it on a hard disk or CD. E-books are published in different formats (e.g. Acrobat adobe and Microsoft Word, Broadband e-books, Compiled HTML, and other formats) and they can be found as static or interactive, however, this study will be looking at e-books in general regales of the formats or type. Also, this research will not attempt to produce a model to predict the future use of e-

books or printed ones. It is mainly a descriptive study to present the current trends of reading. The trendy way of getting an e-book is to acquire a downloadable file of the e-book from a website to be studied from the user's computer or reading device. The user can quickly download the specified book and therefore the readers can bookmark a page, create remarks, emphasize passages, and save chosen text also the readers can comprise lexicon, and modifiable typescript sizes and styles. Some e-books may available at free or at low cost, however, prices. Example: www.digitalbookindex.com.

B. E-Journals

The journal editions available online are called e-journals. Online journals are sequential publications in which the lastyields are made available indigital format and whose contents may or may not be peer-reviewed. There is mainly two media source, i.e., the CD-ROMand Internet, are used for the distribution of the e-journals. Moreover, an e-journal is published and distributed all over the world by the electronic network. E-Journals were developed with the complete text databases obtainable by Dialog in the 1980s. Therefore, an electronic journal is a periodical publication for example weekly, monthly, yearly, etc. which is print in electrical format, usually on the Internet. The researcher/scholar can search either full text or content pages of journals as they can meet with their need to find articles on a particular subject. Another hand, researchers for their need to visit the library to read the journal. Most important they can easily read it on their computer itself and can download the article in electronic format on their computer and can get print out when they want. The reader no needs to worry about the closing time of library because all article or journal is always available in their computer through the internet. The journal does not only contain text format but alsoincludes audio and visual material. So the readers can make their comments to the authors or publishers about the article.

C. E-Zine

The online magazines disseminated through World Wide Web are called E-Zine, which means electronic magazine. Magazines offer many opportunities to today's users that were not available to their predecessors. Because of the multidimensional features of electronic Magazines, they are becoming the choice of news updates, knowledge as well as public activities.

D. Web- Zine

It is a different kind of article or articles which are stored in a server and it will be accessed through a computer with network facility. This online magazine may publish through bulletin board systems or another public network that is the internet. Moreover, if research wants to store particular information or electronic data thus can also download. The important advantage of an online web magazine is that the reader can share their comment to the authors related to the particular article

E. E-Thesis and dissertation (ETD)

Electronic research document in PDF format that is contained details of the thesis and dissertations which were done by the scholars. It is stored in digital format and

researchers all over the world can find the thesis and dissertation if they want to study related work of their research topic. It was formed in the comprehensible works or research of a scholar/Researcher. ETD has enough information and deep knowledge with the scientific sophisticated standard for articulate thoughts with a lesser amount of expensive, simple handling, tiny space, elevated durability, etc. Doctoral research programs are considered to be essential for the development of Higher Education. Moreover, the universities are the key performers in carrying the main responsibility for molding good scholar and researcher at different stages in their career and electronic accessibility of that type document create easiness in their research work.

An electronic newspaper is held information electronically and very easily available through different browsers. Moreover, it is reusable, self-reliant, and refreshable for the user. It's a very important quality of e-newspapers that it found refreshed every day by the concerned editorial boards; it may be audio, video, and text news. Computer with internet facility has to make e-newspaper very convenient to all those who love to the e-newspaper in cooperatively previous days. Last days news may come in the next day by paper but at present, the technology has changed the entire world and news come very fast and right time. Every important piece of news may upload in the e-papers by the editor refreshable and the reader or net surfed can read and download the news at any time as he wants. The e-newspaper is a substitute for normally published papers, through this e-newspaper readers can receive the direct news at any time, it is available in different languages. Moreover, if the reader wants a previous/old newspaper he can also get immediately in e-newspapers from the internet by date wise. So the readers can save time and money and no need to wait for the newspapers. E-newspaper always available on the internet at any time. As we knew today newspaper is becoming a very important part of our life and it is very helpful to all educationist, student, scholar, shopkeeper, businessman, housewives, elderly, politicians, job seekers, teacher, ragman, polishers and other many.

V. ISSUES AND CHALLENGES BY USING E-RESOURCES

In traditional libraries, E-resources are not visible or accessible to the users as to where resources are physically available for browsing and use. Moreover different types of subscriptions are also required as different libraries are given the different packages of different publishers/vendors, as such information sources remain scattered. so it is not convenient for the users to surfing and searching. For better use of such resources need to be united on one platform as it is available at a single stroke of a key. More important users neither have time nor patience for visiting different locations of websites nor search sites.

- Power is the first requirement for e-resource but in India, in many areas, this facility is not available or not properly managed.
- The prominent technology infrastructures for the better accessibility of e-resource are not found.
- Different type of necessitates unique utensils to access e-resource also not available.

- The lake requires compatibility among dissimilar publishers.
- Many challenges related to Hardware and software were raised against to user.
- Patent infringement trouble also a big issue
- These time setup and format of e-book, journals, magazines, etc. may not be legible according to present e-book devices.
- In our country users have not proper awareness and guidance about network skills for the practice of e-resource.
- There is different obstruction and barrier also existed in Technology.
- Many time fear related to lack of Security / Privacy like email hacking and network interruption etc .also raised,
- Without using the technology Technology users don't know to search the books and another soft documental resource.

VI. CONCLUSION

Now we can conclude that now it hard to envisage a world without e-resources. The stipulation and use of e-resources is an element of the complete system, to both the students, institutions, and information professionals. The e-resources assist to deliver the sources to their user very fast, so the user time was saved. Nowadays e-resources have reduced the usage of paper material. These e-resources are convenient to use, reachable at a reasonable cost, and can be accessed from anywhere and by many users concurrently, these databases are most advantageous utilize to put into the academic excellence and achievement of its user community. With the emergence of IT applications in libraries in general and with the advent of the Internet in particular, there is a paradigm shift from traditional print journals to electronic journals in higher education institutions. E-journals have revolution the information-seeking activity of researchers. Information is no longer confined within the four walls of a physical building called a library but is virtually omnipresent in the form of e-journals. Subscription of e-journals and their effective management generates satisfaction among the user community. More and more libraries are redirecting their funds to provide services of e-journals to their users. The bottom line is that with all the advantages of e-journals over their print counterparts, these can be virtually considered as a boon for the higher education libraries, striving for quality and speedy information to its user community. Also, the support provided by consortia subscription adds to the sheer strength of the library by providing e-journals at a highly discounted rate thus enabling the library to meet the increasing pressures of diminishing budgets, increased users expectations, and the rising cost of journals.

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